

Restructuring Of Municipalities and its Impact on Human Resources Staffing, Training & Development Strategies, an Applied Study in Greater Irbid Municipality, Jordan

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Abstract

The purpose of this paper is to identify restructuring of municipalities and its Impact on human resources staffing, training & development strategies, An Applied Study In Greater Irbid Municipality. The importance of the study comes from the importance of municipalities, and the staffing process (recruiting, selection. appointment) & training and development in raising the efficiency of workers. Greater Irbid Municipality was chosen for this study; the sample was (85) persons distributed for (municipality president, a member of the municipal council, department managers, and regions managers) (78) returned, (3) disposed of, (75) analyzed (88%). The study applied certain statistical techniques such as Cronbaeh Alpha, Simple Regression, ANOVA, Percentage, Mean and standard deviation.

The study showed the following results:

- 1. The trends of samples are positive with high degree toward restructuring, staffing process (recruitment, selection, appointment), training & development.*
- 2. There is a statistically significant impact of restructuring on human resources staffing strategies (recruitment, selection, appointment) with weak Pearson correlation.*
- 3. There is a statistically significant impact of the restructuring of municipalities on training with moderate Pearson correlation.*
- 4. There is a statistically significant impact of the restructuring of municipalities on development with weak Pearson correlation.*

The study came up with the following recommendations to the decision makers in Ministry of Municipalities and municipal officials:

- 1. Increased interest in the process of staffing" recruitment, selection and appointment, which will be reflected in performance and efficiency of workers in Jordanian municipalities.*
- 2. Increased interest in training and development of employees, because it's the basis for raising the efficiency and productivity of workers.*
- 4. Make anther research regards to the restructuring of municipalities and its Impact on human resources staffing, training & development strategies in other municipalities in Jordan.*

Key Words – *Restructuring of Municipalities, Human Resources, Staffing, Training, Development, Strategies.*

Introduction

The restructure of municipalities in Jordan began in 1994 when village councils were canceled, and the adjacent municipalities were merged into to one municipality. This was done because there are some financial, human, administrative obstacles and problems facing municipalities. Before the restructure, the number of municipalities was "328" including small, medium, and large municipalities. The decision for merging was taken after extensive studies were done, and the government took experiences from neighboring countries. The number of municipalities reduced to 99 only (Ministry of Municipalities, 2001)

Among the reasons behind, the government taking the restructure decision was administrative, reflected in the failure of municipal councils to achieve their goal in serving citizens. Also, the big number of municipalities, which amounted to 328, increased the number of common service council "58councils". There were financial

reasons represented in insufficient financial sources, weakness in collections, huge expenditures, random employee appointment whose number amounted to (16) thousand in the year 2000, and more than 2000 employees in the common service council, the majority was unqualified, untrained, and their level of education was less than secondary level, some of them were appointed without considering qualifications or required specializations. And others were newly inexperienced graduates with lack necessary experience.. (Temporary Municipality law(No.70, 2002, and law No.21, 2003).

This study aims to know the impact of municipalities restructures on human resources staffing, training & development Strategies in Jordan.

Study Problem and Questions-Municipalities in Jordan and in particular Greater Irbid Municipality are facing several financial, administrative, materialistic and human problems. The major problems are the lack and weakness of administrative, professional employees, insufficient attention for training and development of employees, lack of qualifications and competencies, increase the number of staff allocated in the budget vacancies, which reflected the services of the citizens negatively.

The problem of the study is represented in answers to the following questions:

Does the restructure of municipalities in Jordan affect the strategies of staffing, training and human resources development?

This question is subdivided into the following questions:

- 1- Does the restructure have an impact on the recruitment process?
- 2- Does the restructure have an impact on the selection process?
- 3- Does the restructure have an impact on the appointments process?
- 4- Does the restructure have an impact on the training process?
- 5- Does the restructure have an impact on development process?

Hypotheses of the study

No impact with a statistical indication of municipalities restructures on human resources staffing, training and developing strategies in Jordan. This hypothesis has the following sub-hypotheses:

- 1- No impact with a statistical indication of municipalities restructure on recruitment.
2. No impact with statistical indication of municipalities restructure on selection
3. No impact with a statistical indication of municipalities restructures on appointment
4. No impact with a statistical indication of municipalities restructures on training.
5. No impact with a statistical indication of municipalities restructures on development.

Study model

Important of study

The important of the study comes from the role of municipalities in providing services to the community, and the importance of staffing, training and human resource development in improving the efficiency of employees, also this study will provide heads of municipalities and government to develop the fields of staffing, training, and development municipalities, this study contributes the knowledge to researchers and libraries.

Procedural Definitions:

- **Strategy:** It is the plan of organization in long term, which realizes the competitive ability through preparing resources, to meet needs of the markets, and achievement expectations of enterprises owners. (Johnson, Sholes, 2002)
- **Restructure:** It is the process concerned with official relations among the constituents of the organization that implies: strategy groups, plans, programs, and policies, prescribed by the management to reduce costs, improve operation proficiency, in addition to improve the competitive ability of the organization, through reducing employees number, administrative units, to achieve the goal of the organization. (Kieselbach et al.,2009)
- **Municipality:** A national institution which is independent financially and administratively, provides various services to citizens. (Jordanian Law of municipalities, 2014).
- **Staffing:** One of the primary jobs of human resources department, recruiting employees with the quantity, quality number, (Al humood, et al., 2001).
- **Recruitment:** Finding qualified applicants to choose the best from them to fill a specific job. (Al humood, et al., 2001)
- **Selection:** It is the process of choosing qualifications persons who have the necessary and appropriate for certain positions in the organization. (Al humood, et al., 2001)
- **Appointments:** Appointing the person chosen for the required job, that fits person's potentials. (Al humood, et al., 2001)
- **Training:** Training is efforts that aim to provide the employee with information, knowledge, development of his skills, knowledge, expertise, including increasing the efficiency (Sakarnieh, 2012).
- **Development:** Acquire the knowledge, skills, and behaviors of employees, that improve the ability of employees for meeting the challenges facing the current business and future. (Sakarnieh, 2012)
- **Strategic Staffing:** Is a process of defining and addressing staffing implications of strategic and operational plans. Staffing includes "recruitment, hiring, promotion, training, development and classification.(Anfuso,1995)

Literature Review

A. Restructuring:

(1) The concept of Restructuring:

Restructuring can be defined as an organizational change that is much more significant than a common place change and affects at least a whole organizational sector, or an entire company rather than focusing on peripheral changes in work practices. (Kieselbach et al,2009)

(2) Forms of restructuring

- **Relocation:** The activity stays within the same company, but is relocated to another location within the same country.
- **Offshoring/delocalization:** The activity is outsourced outside the country's borders.
- **Outsourcing:** The activity is subcontracted to another company within the same country.
- **Bankruptcy/closure:** An industrial site is closed, or a company goes bankrupt for economic reasons not directly connected to relocation or outsourcing.

- **Merger/acquisition.** Two companies merge, or a company is undertaking acquisitions which then involve an internal restructuring programmed.
- **Internal restructuring:** The company undertakes a job-cutting plan or other forms of restructuring that are not linked to a type as defined above.
- **Business expansion:** A company extends its business activities, hiring new workforce..(Kieselbach etal,2009).

B. Local management (Municipality):

(1) The concept of Local Management

The concept of local management appeared at the beginning of the 19th. This concept has several definitions. (Mawhood, 1983) Defined it as a body of citizens with a moral identity, which runs services needed by the community. It was also defined as one of the administration methods by which area of the country are divided into local units monitored by a council that represents general administration of that unit. These councils have financially and administratively autonomous. (Al Maani, Abu Faris, 2005)

In Jordan, the creation of such municipal councils goes back to 1880. Since then, the number of them kept growing till it ended with (328) municipalities, by the end of the 20th c, they adopted the Ottoman law of municipalities till (1925), when the first municipal law was issued in the Emirate of East Jordan in (1926). In 1955 the municipal law No.29 was issued. That law defined the municipality to be a national body that is financially and administratively autonomous. It has the authority to modernize, nullify, and recruit, within its boundaries in compliance with the prescribed laws.

(2) Classification of municipalities: The municipalities were classified into four categories. (Abu Faris, Al-Maani, 2006)

- **First class:** municipalities of governorate centers, and any municipality whose population exceeds one hundred thousand people.
- **Second class:** municipalities of district centers, and other municipalities whose population is between 15,000-100,000 persons.
- **Third class:** municipalities of region centers, the population is between 5,000- 15,000 persons.
- **Fourth class:** other municipalities.

(3) Reasons of the restructuring of municipalities:

Most of the municipal councils suffer from difficult financial conditions due to weak financial revenues and the heavy burdens these councils shoulder. Such a thing is reflected the low level of service given to citizens. Till the end of 2000, municipality's debts amounted "94" Million Jordanian Dinars. Ninety municipalities were on the brink of bankruptcy, because of low collections and incompetent administration. In July 2001, the actual implementation of margin municipalities started, and the number of municipalities in Jordan amounted to 99, excluding Amman Greater municipality. The program of merging municipalities aims at:

- Employing technical machinery and equipment in a way to save money.
- Facilitating the training and the qualifying of municipality employees.
- Controlling construction growth in all neighboring municipalities.
- Preparing organizational plans in a more comprehensive way for all neighboring municipalities.
- Increasing municipal capacity to deliver better services to citizens
- Preserving agricultural land by not using it exploited for housing purpose

C. Training and Development of Human Resources Management

(1) The concept of training and development

Training is a learning process during which individuals acquire skills and knowledge which help them to achieve their targets. And also the training should be associated with the nature of acts and consistent with the policies and the plans of the organization. Training performing is identified a planned efforts that aim to facilitate the learning process of the personnel (knowledge, skills, and behaviors) which is related to their works.

Although training and development are two identical concepts regarding the methods used to get the education, they are different in terms of time.

Training is more targeted to our present day as it focuses on the current jobs for individuals and immediately. As for development, it focuses on the future jobs in the organization, as well as is interested in education more than training for the worker on a limited work. (Denisi, Griffin, 2001, 45).

(2) The important of Training & Development

Training process within organizations has a great importance in the development of staff working and prepares them for integration into the labor market. The organization which wants to be distinguished from other institutions in the same field, it has to provide the skilled staff; capable of dealing with the new technology, and that cannot be achieved except through systematic training programs based on a scientific basis to give the staff the required skills. Training is an activity planned by a scientific method for achieving the future goals; and which aims to make changes in the trainees regarding information, skills, experiences, attitudes and performance scores, working methods, behaviors and commitment to the values of the organization in which the trainees work.

The training also is one of the significant ways and means by which the organization resorts for learning, developing and improving the competencies and skills and experiences of their "human resources" which are one of the most important sources of "wealth" owned by the organization, as the investment in these human resources is one of the most important investments in organizations and companies. Training became a contemporary necessity for organizations as represent the tremendous technological developments in our world today. The training is the lifeline now for these organizations and those companies; it is an important tool and for development and prosperity of the human resources and then societies as well as to achieve high productivity rates for these organizations to enables them to achieve high profitability returns. There are many studies and researches that showed that the training plays a major role the social and cultural growth in societies, and the training is the basis for all learning and development of the human resource.

The successful organizations that are seeking for training and developing the personnel to achieve their targets in the growth and development, the personnel are the means for the organization to achieve its targets, therefore it is necessary to develop the skills and abilities of personnel continuously, the new employee who recently enrolled in the organization may not has some skills and experience to perform job duties efficiently. Hence the importance of training appears in acquiring the new worker the skills that make him able to perform the anticipated duties in a satisfactory manner.

On the other hand, training is required for the purpose of workers preparation to occupy these posts with the highest level of difficulty and responsibility that require higher levels of skills and capabilities, the importance of training appears in the development and evolvement of the worker's abilities to occupy the posts and positions with the highest level, that they will be promoted to it, the importance of training is not limited to the development of the workers' abilities to such information and arts associated with the job performance but extended to include the improvement and development the behaviors of the workers at the work and his dealing with the organization, colleagues, presidents, subordinates and all the people in the organization. . (Denisi, Griffin, 2001,66)

Previous studies

(A) Study Al magarbah, (2012) **the impact of the merger in municipalities' performance**, a field study on the municipalities of the Hashemite Kingdom of Jordan. This study aimed to investigate the impact of merging municipalities on the performance of the application on the municipalities of the Kingdom of Jordan process, The study population consisted of all municipal managers(250), included municipal managers which were merged, the study reached the following results, the process of merging municipalities affected the development of employees efficiency, and improved financial aspects and increased the quality of services provided to citizens, there are differences in attitudes among respondents about the performance of municipalities due to gender, marital status, age and educational qualification.

(B) Study Hebdon, Jalette(2008)**The restructuring of municipal services: a Canada – United States comparison.**

This study examines how cities and towns provide services in the United States, and Canada, the study of the selection of the most effective form of service delivery is particularly instructive at the local level of government because that is where the change occurred first and where most research has been focused. Research shows that Canadians have a more coordinated market economy, a greater faith in government, and more communitarian values. Thus we hypothesize that Canadian municipalities will offer more services overall, but fewer through the private sector than their American counterparts. Canadian municipalities provided more services than their American counterparts. Contrary to expectations, however, Canadian local governments had higher rates of privatized services and greater numbers of privatization plans.

(C) Study Abu Faris & Almaane (2006) **Impact of merging municipalities in Jordan on administrative and financial efficiency**, from the viewpoint of the heads of councils "field study." This study aimed to identify the impact of the merging municipalities in Jordan, on the administrative and financial efficiency, from the viewpoint of the heads of councils. The study population consisted of the heads of the Jordanian municipal councils (99) President, The study results showed there is a significant relationship between the merging of municipalities, administrative and financial efficiency, And there are no statistically significant differences in the process of merging the municipalities on the administrative and financial efficiency due to the variable municipal class differences.

(D) Study Al maitah(2005) **The impact of the restructuring on the performance of municipal services**, "An Empirical Study on the municipalities of the southern governorates centers" Karak, Tafileh, Ma'an. This study aimed to identify the reality of local management in Jordan, and analyze the impact of the restructuring on the of municipality performance in the municipalities of the southern governorates centers, and the impact of each of the "gender, age, experience, job title, educational level" on the restructuring of municipalities and performance of services, To achieve the study objectives, the questionnaire distributed to the sample's "600" employees, the study reached the following result.

1. The restructuring led to the creation of highly improved in the field of financial and legislative reform, and moderately in the field of administrative side.
2. The performance of service came highly in organizational services, environmental services, a medium degree in service roads.
3. There is a statistically significant effect between independent variables and the dependent variable.

(E) characteristics of the study:

This study is characterized by being the only in Jordan and in the world for the knowledge & the researcher, which dealt with the restructuring of municipalities and its impact on staffing and, training, development strategies of human resources, also its dealt with a number of concepts(restructuring of municipalities, staffing, training and development strategies. Irbid Municipality was chosen for the study being one of the major municipalities in Jordan and used several studies to achieve the goals and results of the study.

Results and Discussion

Two types of data have been adopted in this study, namely; secondary data, represented in the published literature in books, journals, previous studies and periodical journal related to the study. Primary data, which are the questionnaires. These questionnaires were distributed on Greater Irbid Municipality in the north area of Jordan. The final sample size was (85) questionnaires for (municipality President, Member of the municipal council, department managers, and regions managers).

The questionnaire consisted of two parts, the first aimed at collecting identification data about the subject, such as:(job, gender, education, specialization, age, experience). The second part aimed at measuring the study variables, which consisted of one independent variable (Restructuring of municipalities) and five dependent variables (recruitment, selection, appointment, training, development).

The second part was formulated in a form that enables easy measuring, since 5- point Likert scale was adopted: to a very strongly agree(5), agree(4), no certain(3), not agree(2), strongly not agree(1).

To discuss the reliability of the questionnaire results and the coherence between its questions, it was submitted to selected management teaching staff members in universities and selected experts in the field off

to get their feedback and responses. The questionnaire was also subject to reliability analysis to measure Alpha Cornbach coefficient, which was found to be (0.895).

Thus, the conclusions of the questionnaire are considered reliable to the realization of the study objectives.

To achieve the objectives of the study and test its hypothesis, the analytical, descriptive, causal approach was used to show how the restructuring of municipalities impact on human resources staffing, training & development strategies. Simple regression model and One-Way ANOVA with regression were used to test the hypotheses.

The questionnaire's answers were transformed into a worksheet using SPSS. The results were as follows:

A. Characteristics of Respondents

Sample characteristics include five major items in this study: (1) job, (2) gender.(3) Education, (4) specialization, (5) age (6) experience. Table 1 shows the results obtained after analyzing identification variables. The frequency percentage for each variable is listed according to the survey categories in the table.

Reliability Test:

A Cranach Alpha test was used to ascertain instrument reliability. The value was = 0.895 for the questionnaire. All values are accepted since they are more than 0.60. Table (1) reveals Cranach's' Alpha test for each item in the questionnaire.

Table (1) Reliability analysis of the study scales

Variables	Cranach's alpha value
restructuring	0.872
recruitment	0.673
selection	0.617
recruitment	0.733
training	0.832
development	0.879

The result showed alpha for each variable is greater than accepted percent 0.60, which is a reasonable value indicating the tool consistency that enhanced its use for the study.

Analysis and discussion

Frequency and percentages were computed for the sample's characteristics.

Table (2) Sample's Distribution According to Demographic Information

Category	Frequency	Percentage%
Job		
president	1	1.3
Member of the municipal council	25	33.3
regional manager	20	26.7
department managers	29	38.7
Total	75	100.0
Total	75	100.0
Gender		
Male	59	78.7
Female	16	21.3
Total	75	100.0
Education		
High studies	15	20.0
Bachelor	35	46.7
Diploma	12	16.0
High school	13	17.3
Total	75	100.0
specialization		
Engineering	26	34.7
Management Science	19	25.3
Humanities	3	4.0
Space science	7	9.3
others	20	26.7
Total	75	100.0
Age		
Less than 30 years	3	4.0
30-40 years	20	26.7
41-50 years	27	36.0
Above 50 years	25	33.3
Total	75	100.0
Experience		
Less than 5 years	17	22.7
5-10 years	18	24.0
Above 10 years	40	53.3
Total	75	100.0

The table above indicates that the highest percentage of the sample is working as department managers, whereas 21% of the sample has a diploma or less, 46.7% of the sample has a bachelor degree. The above table also shows that there are more males (78.7%) than females, the table shows that 34.7% of the sample is

specialized in engineering, whereas 36% of the sample is between 41-50 years old. Finally, it is found that the highest percentage of the sample (53.3%) has 10 years' experience.

Analysis of the questionnaire paragraphs

Mean and standard deviation are used to describe attitudes toward following questions:

Table (3) Mean and standard deviation of the restructuring variable

paragraphs	Mean	Std. Deviation
1. The restructure greatly helped in the municipality artistic, administrative and financial capabilities.	3.7333	.75933
2. The restructure greatly helped in the increment of municipality revenues.	3.8800	.73448
3. The restructure greatly helped in the reduction of municipality expenditures.	3.3867	.91376
4.The restructure contributed to the reduction of municipality debts.	3.6267	.88185
5.The restructure leads to improving services given to citizens.	3.8667	.79412
6. The restructure made the administrative body more effective.	3.7067	.86639
Grand Mean	3.7000	.64666

Examining the above table, it can be seen that there is a positive attitude from participants towards the above variable. This appeared through the mean of the paragraphs which scored higher than 3.00 referring to the paragraph as a good indicator. The most influential paragraph variable was (2) with a mean of (3.88)

Table (4) Mean and standard deviation of the attraction variable

paragraphs	Mean	Std. Deviation
7.The restructure made recruitment better.	3.6667	.74132
8.The municipality tends to hire employees of its region.	3.8267	.70468
9.The municipality announces about its needs for employees through different means of publicity.	3.7467	.75504
10.The restructure helped in hiring professionals to the municipality.	3.4933	.84427
11.The municipality offers a tempting way to recruit professionals and experienced.	3.1467	.96833
Grand Mean	3.5760	.53217

Examining the above table, it can be seen that there is a positive attitude from participants towards the above variable. This appeared through the mean of the paragraphs which scored higher than 3.00 referring to the paragraph as a good indicator. The most influential paragraph of the variable was (8) with a mean of (3.8267).

Table (5) Mean and standard deviation of the selection variable

paragraphs	Mean	Std. Deviation
12. The municipality Investigating justice when conducting the selection process.	3.1467	.71079
13.The municipality takes into consideration geographical distribution.	3.4000	.73521
14-The selection process is based on the compatibility of qualification to the job description.	3.4933	.68524
15.Interviews and exams are conducted by the municipality to ensure the competence of employees.	3.5600	.68260
16- Some steps in the process of selection are done informally.	3.6400	.76476
17. In selecting employees, the municipality takes into consideration Recommendations of officials in charge.	3.4933	.76004
Grand Mean	3.4556	.42389

Examining the above table, it can be seen that there is a positive attitude from participants towards the above variable. This appeared through the mean of the paragraphs which scored higher than 3.00 referring to the paragraph as a good indicator. The most influential paragraph of the variable was (16) with a mean of (3.64)

Table (6) Mean and standard deviation of the recruitment variable

paragraphs	Mean	Std. Deviation
18. Outside recommendation plays an important role in appointments.	3.6533	.79684
19. The number of employees in the municipality exceeds the number of jobs.	3.7600	1.03767
20. Some employees are assigned jobs that do not fit their qualifications.	3.6800	.85677
21. The municipality adopts the principle of the suitable person for the suitable job.	3.0800	.67303
22. The restructure decreased relative hiring.	2.8133	.76571
23. All employees hired after the restructure occupy the jobs assigned to them.	3.1867	.95427
24. After the restructure, the municipality endeavors to achieve excellence in human resources.	3.1067	.62759
Grand Mean	3.3257	.51270

Examining the above table, it can be seen that there is a positive attitude from participants towards the above variable except paragraph (22). This appeared through the mean of the paragraphs which scored higher than 3.00 referring to the paragraph as a good indicator. The most influential paragraph of the variable was (19) with a mean of (3.76)

Table (7) Mean and standard deviation of the training variable

paragraphs	Mean	Std. Deviation
25. After the staffing process, the municipality works for qualifying and training the employees.	3.8400	.54624
26. The needs for training are related to the needs of individuals and job need.	3.6267	.63189
27. The municipality cares for constant training of employees.	3.6667	.75933
28. The performance of employees showed great progress after the restructure	3.7333	.55345
29. Fairness of training opportunities given to individuals was after restructure	3.2400	.71357
30. planning for training was taken care of after the restructure.	3.6000	.78843
Grand Mean	3.6178	.49530

Examining the table, it can be seen that there is a positive attitude from participants towards the above variable. This appeared through the mean of the paragraphs which scored higher than 3.00 referring to the paragraph as a good indicator. The most influential paragraph of the variable was (25) with a mean of (3.84)

Table (8) Mean and standard deviation of the development variable

paragraphs	Mean	Std. Deviation
31. Training met my job needs after the restructure.	3.4267	.73839
32. My job knowledge developed after the restructuring.	3.3467	.68760
33. The goal of developing the employees is the major concern of the municipalities.	3.3733	.63189
34. The municipality gets its employees in decision making pertained to their specialization.	3.6133	.75146
35. The municipality works on correct planning regarding jobs.	3.5067	.74204
36. The municipality prepares and develops employees to occupy better positions in the future.	3.3067	.75289
Grand Mean	3.4289	.56763

Examining the table, it can be seen that there is a positive attitude from participants towards the above variable. This appeared through the mean of the paragraphs which scored higher than 3.00 referring to the paragraph as a good indicator. The most influential paragraph of the variable was (34) with a mean of (3.61)

HYPOTHESES TESTING

The hypotheses of the study will be as follows:

- There is no statistically significant impact of restructuring on human resources staffing, training, and development strategies.

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.443 ^a	.196	.185	.31747

a. Predictors: (Constant), ind

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	1.795	1	1.795	17.807	.000 ^b
	Residual	7.357	73	.101		
	Total	9.152	74			

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Coefficients		
1	(Constant)	2.581	.214		12.045	.000
	ind	.241	.057	.443	4.220	.000

Linear Regression is used to test the hypothesis; it is found that a calculated value of (F) is significant at (0.05) level. This means that null is rejected, which means that there are a statistically significant impact of restructuring on human resources staffing, training and development strategies with moderate Pearson correlation 0.443

The sub-hypotheses of the study will be:

- 1. There is no statistically significant impact of restructuring on recruiting.**

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted Square	R Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.255 ^a	.065	.052	.51809

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	1.363	1	1.363	5.076	.027 ^b
	Residual	19.594	73	.268		
	Total	20.957	74			

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Coefficients		
1	(Constant)	2.800	.350		8.005	.000
	ind	.210	.093	.255	2.253	.027

Linear Regression is used to test the hypothesis; it is found that a calculated value of (F) is significant at (0.05) level. This means that null is rejected, which means that there is a statistically significant impact of restructuring on recruiting with weak Pearson correlation 0.255

- 2. There is no statistically significant impact of restructuring on selection.**

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted Square	R Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.257 ^a	.066	.053	.41239

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
	Regression	.881	1	.881	5.182	.026 ^b
1	Residual	12.415	73	.170		
	Total	13.296	74			

Coefficients

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	2.831	.278		10.169	.000
	ind	.169	.074	.257	2.276	.026

Linear Regression is used to test the hypothesis; it is found that a calculated value of (F) is significant at (0.05) level. This means that null is rejected, which means that there is a statistically significant impact of restructuring on selection with weak Pearson correlation 0.257

There is no statistically significant impact of restructuring on appointment.

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted Square	R Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.245 ^a	.060	.047	.50042

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
	Regression	1.171	1	1.171	4.675	.034 ^b
1	Residual	18.281	73	.250		
	Total	19.451	74			

Coefficients

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	2.606	.338		7.714	.000
	ind	.195	.090	.245	2.162	.034

Linear Regression is used to test the hypothesis; it is found that a calculated value of (F) is significant at

(0.05) level. This means that null is rejected, which means that there is a statistically significant impact of restructuring on recruitment with weak Pearson correlation 0.245

3. There is no statistically significant impact of restructuring on training.

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted Square	R Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.552 ^a	.305	.296	.41567

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
	Regression	5.541	1	5.541	32.070	.000 ^b
1	Residual	12.613	73	.173		
	Total	18.154	74			

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	2.052	.281		7.313	.000
	ind	.423	.075	.552	5.663	.000

Linear Regression is used to test the hypothesis; it is found that a calculated value of (F) is significant at (0.05) level. This means that null is rejected, which means that there is a statistically significant impact of restructuring on training with moderate Pearson correlation 0.552.

There is no statistically significant impact of restructuring on development**Model Summary**

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted Square	R Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.240 ^a	.057	.045	.55484

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
	Regression	1.370	1	1.370	4.450	.038 ^b
1	Residual	22.473	73	.308		
	Total	23.843	74			

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error			
	(Constant)	2.650	.375		7.076	.000
1	ind	.210	.100	.240	2.110	.038

Linear Regression is used to test the hypothesis; it is found that a calculated value of (F) is significant at (0.05) level. This means that null is rejected, which means that there is a statistically significant impact of restructuring on development with weak Pearson correlation 0.24

Results:

The study examined the restructuring of municipalities and its impact on human resources staffing, training & development strategies, An applied study In Irbid Greater Municipality The study showed the following results:

1. The trends of samples are positive with high degree toward restructuring.
2. 1. The trends of samples are positive with high degree toward recruitment.
3. The trends of samples are positive with a high degree of selection.
4. The trends of samples are positive with high degree toward an appointment.
5. The trends of samples are positive with a high degree of training.
6. The trends of samples are positive with a high degree of development.
7. There is a significant impact with statistically significant to the restructuring of municipalities on human resources staffing, training & development strategies in Irbid Municipality with moderate Pearson correlation.
8. There is a significant impact with statistically significant to the restructuring of municipalities on recruitment with weak Pearson correlation.
9. There is significant impact with statistically significant to the restructuring of municipalities on selection with weak Pearson correlation

10. There is a significant impact with statistically significant to the restructuring of municipalities on an appointment with weak Pearson correlation.
11. There is a significant impact with statistically significant to the restructuring of municipalities on training with moderate Pearson correlation.
12. There is a significant impact with statistically significant to the restructuring of municipalities on development with weak Pearson correlation.

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